

INFLUENCE OF AFRICAN MAGIC URBAN “WIVES ROUND TABLE” TV PROGRAMME ON THE PARENTING ROLES OF WOMEN IN IMO STATE.

¹Okeke, Culbert Chukwudi, ²Ihechu, Paschal Innocent, Ph. D. and ³Osuagwu, Gladys Amarachi

Email: culbercan2016@gmail.com; 08038745664/ ipi@abiastateuniversity.edu.ng; madinopas@yahoo.com; +234-706-5138-607/ gladysosuagwu@abiastateuniversity.edu.ng; osuagwu.amara@gmail.com; +2347065225880

Article Info

Keywords: Influence, African Magic Urban, TV Programme, Parenting, Women.

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.15412162

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the influence of the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV Programme on the Parenting Roles of Women in Imo State. The major objectives of the study were to ascertain the extent to which Imo state women are exposed to “Wives Round Table” programme on African magic Urban and to determine the extent to which African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programmes has influenced the parenting role of women in Imo state. Using the survey research method, the researcher sought the opinions of women residents in the three senatorial zones in Imo state who watch the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme. The Cultivation Analysis theory as well as The Reinforcement Theory served as the theoretical frameworks for the study. The population of this study was 5,459,300, out of which 385 women in Imo state were sampled from the three senatorial zones in Imo state. The questionnaire was used as the survey instrument for data collection. The study found that women in Imo state are highly exposed to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban. It was also revealed that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme to a great extent, has influenced the parenting roles of women in Imo state. This was because there was an improvement in the parenting skills of the women as they could easily balance their parenting roles as a mother with their career roles. Based on the findings, the researcher therefore recommends that media houses constantly come up with family-related programmes for their audience, as that is one of their social responsibility to the people. They should also allocated more time to family and parenting related programmes, and bring professionals onboard to provided more details on parenting issues.

INTRODUCTION

The media play a significant role in the lives of humans. The significance of television is rapidly assuming a highly imperative position throughout the world. It is an electronic medium of mass communication and has generally become valuable in this present dispensation owing the fact that it has the characteristics of sound, vision, and movement.

According to (Pechu, 2014), television is an electronic communication medium that allows for the transmission of real time visual images with sound. In addition, television has been defined as an electronic device used to receive sound and images that create television programmes that people watch.

Every day as people glue their eyes to their TV sets, there is this tendency to want to feel what is being broadcast. Television now presents itself as the reality appropriate medium for them to achieve that. Thus, families now stick to television, watching their favourite programmes at their convenience. Families are basic, foundational social units in human communities. In today's technological world, media and other technologies have influenced the communication level between family members to an extent. Here, family communication cannot be seen only as the verbal and non-verbal behavior which occurs within the family; it is much more than the exchange of words. It is what we say, how we say it, why we say it, when we say it, and what we neglect to say. Verbal communication will be used to solve problems, and nonverbal communication like eye contact, use of gestures, touch, space, time, and facial expressions will also help family members to obtain information from one another. This kind of interpersonal relationship communication helps family members develop shared or co-constructed meanings concerning their lives and relationships, as well as the roles played by parents in the family (Sriram & Kumar, 2014).

Media and technology play a major role in a family's life, everybody in the family uses different media and technology to communicate among themselves. The structure and communication among family members have changed drastically in a way that no one could have expected. In this information and technological age, family members depend on some media to increase the volume of messages and act accordingly. Interpersonal communication, family meetings, and face-to-face communication activities have started declining; that media has adopted that place slowly.

According to Sriram and Kumar (2014), in their study stated that the relationship between family and television should not be separated. Their research discusses how television influences conceptions of adults and children in their family and marriage life and how media portrayals reflect and reinforce views about the nature of family in society. Family members can watch television to be together or to get away from each other; as a basis for talk or to avoid interaction; as a source of conflict or an escape from it. Because much of the time family members spend together in the presence of television, television at least partially defines the context within which family interactions occur and therefore helps determine the meaning of such interactions.

According to Egbai (2021), television can generate both positive and negative effects, and many studies have examined the impact of television on society, particularly women. The women's developmental level is a critical factor in determining whether television and other media have positive or negative effects. Television viewing frequently limits girls' time for vital activities such as playing, reading, learning to talk, spending time with peers and family, storytelling, participating in regular exercise, and developing other necessary physical, mental, and social skills, according to several studies. Television has a strong influence on consumers, including women and children. Even their parents

Say that television viewing, gaming, internet use and mobile usage are easy to manage their kids because they do not disturb them much.

Parenting is the duty of a parent (Father and Mother) who works interchangeably to ensure that their child is raised in a conducive environment of love, guidance, support, care, direction, and encouragement. Parenting is the biggest sacrifice one can make; it puts one's life on hold to fulfill the promise of your children's tomorrow. Parenting is one of the most rewarding and challenging responsibilities. It is a long journey that requires courage, determination, and patience (Peterson, 2022).

The role of a woman/mother regarding parenting is extremely essential. In addition to child bearing, the woman or mother has lot of roles to play as a care giver, supporter, guardian, director, etc. As a working woman and a mother, two responsibilities are placed before you, but your ability to manage both responsibilities properly makes you a better woman/mother. According to Thomas (2021), quoting Lois Leke Amoo on "motherhood thingy", "women are life wire of every home and as such, key to raising wholesome kids that make a healthy society". A Mother/woman Plays a unique role and have a great impact as they affect a child's life socially, culturally, educationally, spiritually, and psychologically.

African Magic Urban "Wives Round Table" is a TV show/programme that gives women and their families' access to valuable and authentic information, tools, opportunities, and resources to help them lead or live a fulfilled life. The show also gives people, especially women, a platform to express their views, opinions, and experiences on various life matters. The show have a reflection of true life stories, in-depth analysis, valuable information, opportunities to listen to multiple perspectives (it gives room for peoples opinion and judgments), and lessons to learn. The show was first hosted on July 7th 2022 by a family life counselor Amaka Chibuzo-Obi and viewed every Wednesday, with different episodes and topics on African Magic Urban on DSTV/GOTV channel 153 from 8:30 pm.

The television programme, "Wives Round Table" can be a powerful influence in developing the value system and shaping behavior of most women/mothers; hence, this study sets out to ascertain its influence on the parenting roles of women in Imo state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The traditional family is no longer just one man serving as the breadwinner and one woman as the caretaker, and society's ideas of those roles are also shifting. Hence, programmes or shows such as "Wives Round Table" that highlight the different roles of parents are believed to influence viewers. Scholars have conducted studies on the roles of the media on family, especially through social media and television platforms, but there seems to be a disputable lacuna on issues bothering the influence of TV programmes on the parenting roles of women. It has therefore become pertinent to investigate the benefits acquired from the programme in relation to how women in general learn parenting and their behavior through the programmes episodes. Hence, to what extent has African magic's "Wives Round Table" TV programme influenced the parenting roles of women in Imo State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were:

1. To ascertain the extent Imo state women are exposed to "Wives Round Table" programme on African magic Urban.
2. To understand the perception of women in Imo state about "Wives Round Table" programme on African Magic Urban TV channel.
3. To determine the extent to which African Magic Urban "Wives Round Table" TV programmes has influenced the parenting role of women in Imo state.

Literature Review

The live nature of television allows it to transmit visuals and information almost instantly. This capacity of television makes it ideal for transmitting live visuals of news and various events. Several audiences who cannot read or can read television can access the information shown on television. As a medium of communication, television also has a very wide output, range and reach. By nature, television has generally been identified as a transitory medium of communication. It is different from other communication media. It combines compelling visuals with the personal immediacy of radio. This audio–visual character gives television a great power in conveying realism, which keeps viewers emotionally involved with the programme (Johnson, 2021).

It allows audiences to witness various events which occur around the world. The new media will enable audiences to participate in various events by posting their comments on websites. Television offers several advantages to mankind: it can be used for a variety of purposes. It can be used to demonstrate processes or physical skills, to show movement, to enrich reading skills, to make distance learning more personalized, and to make teaching and learning very attractive and dynamic. Television provides different kinds of programmes for different sections of society. Today, people spend most time watching a variety of television programmes both domestic and foreign. It is very well said that television is the heavy weight of all mass media. Nicholas Johnson (2021) observes: “Television is one of the most powerful forces men has ever unleashed upon himself”.

Women and Television Programmes

Television is a powerful broadcasting medium that appeals to the senses of sight and hearing. Programmes displayed on televisions have a fast impact on the viewer because people often believe in what they see. This medium performs three basic function which is; to inform, educate, and entertain its viewers through the programmes it displays. The women are very much attracted to television shows that are known for glamor. Experience reveals that television can introduce women to several things, issues, trends, and developments related to the environment and development. The kinds of messages women receive from television affect their perceptions of others. Young female children aged below six years usually face some difficulty in determining the difference between fantasy and reality on television.

A review of the research on women and television conducted in this decade also revealed that the largest proportion of ‘effects’ studies focused on aggression and sexuality specifically.

Another scholar, Ngozi Eze (2017), asserted in her findings that there is a lack of compartment between the traditional societal roles demarcated for Nigerian women and modern women’s pursuit of careers, especially leadership roles, which can hinder women’s career advancements. The results revealed that the change was complicated by Nigerian cultural norms, which required women to maintain their households nearly singlehandedly, despite the additional time they needed to dedicate to their careers. Therefore, gender equality and equal access to opportunities for women to advance socially, economically, and politically remain issues in Nigeria. The study recommended that mentors, workshops, seminars, and premarital and marital counseling, among others, be provided to women to address the problem in view of the changing roles of women in Nigeria. Future researchers should also identify more sustainable dual professional role solutions for women who are interested in pursuing a career while maintaining a family.

There are a plethora of television channels that offer greater choice and quality (both positive and negative) of programming to mankind. Television is now an interactive experience with women being able to interact digitally as they watch and continue the experience online. It is clear that Television viewing, like any life experience, needs to be managed and monitored in the very young, with supervision decreasing as the young women audience learns to appropriately manage their own viewing behavior, critically evaluate what they view and discuss any

issues or concerns that come out of what they have viewed. Contemporary research has highlighted that for many families, television is an essential part of modern culture, and it needs to be monitored and managed with increasing parental confidence given advances in technology.

It is important that women are supported and feel empowered through their own management choices and their use of the available broadcasting technologies, which have provided the benefit of connectivity to mankind (Johnson, 2021).

Role of Parents in Child Upbringing

The importance of parents exists due to several important roles they play in the life of their children. Some of these ideas are discussed below, according to Kretchmar-Hendricks (2023).

Care: Caring parents protect their children from any sort of physical, mental, or emotional harm. In other words, it enhances and improves the emotional and physical health of children.

Protection: Parents protect their children by setting safe boundaries for them. Children will know from an early age what they are allowed to do and what not to do. They will also learn the social and cultural ethics of their society in this way.

Development: It considers the potential of children constructively. Furthermore, it enhanced potential results that yield better opportunities for children in the future. Parenting is a lifetime job that does not allow one to step back. Parents play a major role in enhancing the physical, mental, spiritual as well as cognitive development of an individual. The importance of parents in child development is of utmost significance. It is so because it is only the parents who are selfless toward their children, desire success for their children, and will work hard to see it become a reality. Parenting is a strong and friendly relationship.

Provide a foundation for their beliefs: A child goes through several phases during their development from an infant to an adult. They begin by becoming a family member and continue to become members of a society, community, religious community, school, and much more. Parents provide assistance throughout all phases. They also help them learn the various principles necessary to move within society and help them differentiate between right and wrong.

Guidance and support: Parents provide continuous support to their children. They are also the ones who encourage their kids. They help children master important developmental tasks. The role of parents is significant because they are the primary social group that a child deals with in his early years.

Provide a healthy and good lifestyle: Parents influence the lives of their children in a way that no other person can influence. They play a key role in the emotional and academic development of their children or child's life. A better academic direction helps children in forming successful careers and enjoy a successful life financially. A mother's role for her child is accomplished by her love, patience, support, and sacrifice she makes in the life of the child.

Theoretical Framework

For this work, the Cultivation Analysis theory, as well as The Reinforcement Theory served as the theoretical frameworks for the study.

Cultivation Analysis Theory

The theory, also known as cultivation hypothesis or cultivation analysis, was originally propounded by Professor G. Gerbner, Dean of the Annenberg School of Communications. Professor Gerbner was later joined by Larry Gross during the 60's. The central tenet of cultivation theory is that people's social construction of reality is primarily shaped by what they see on television. Put in another way, the more people spend time watching

programmes on television, the more likely they are to believe the social reality of people, places and things portrayed via the medium.

According to Gerbner and Gross (1976), cited in Asemah, Nwammuo and Uwaoma (2017), the mass media, particularly television, speaks to audiences and maintains society through images and ideas. Therefore, cultivation theory explains how people's conceptions of social reality are influenced by their television exposure. The theory simply assumes that people's attitudes are forged in the hours they watch television, especially in the direction in which the content flows ideologically. Although Gerbner and his team focused their research on only fictional television, scholars have, in recent times, expanded cultivation research into additional media such as video games and cinematic films (Hernandez, 2012; Vinney, 2019).

In relation to this study, the cultivation analysis theory helps explain how the exposure of women to television programmes such as "*Wives Round Table*" on Africa Magic Urban has a way of influencing their parenting roles, as these women might have the tendency of wanting to implement the advice they get exposed to on the programme which will in turn affect their parenting skills either positively or negatively depending on their level of exposure to the programme. Therefore, this theory is very pertinent to this study as it sheds light on how influencing television content can affect the viewing audience.

Re-Enforcement Theory

In 1960, theorist Joseph Klapper proposed Reinforcement Theory. The Reinforcement Theory states that the more that an audience of mass medium is exposed to certain ideas and stimuli, the more likely it is to accept such ideas and experience behavioral changes directly traceable to the communicated stimulus. Klapper cited Ukaegbu (2018), arguing that people's attitudes, beliefs and behavior was more likely to be influenced by their family, schools, communities, and religious institutions. He argued that the only time the media could influence people was when it introduced a new idea or concept.

Relating this theory to the study, this theory suggests that the media influences culture in three ways: the programmes or features content can reinforce the existing pattern of cultural practices and make people believe that certain social forms (norms) are being maintained by society. The media can also bring or highlight new findings or ways of improving or modernizing existing cultural norms with which the public has little experience, and media can change existing norms and consequently convert people from one view or behavior to another. This suggests that programmes such as "*Wives Round Table*" on Africa Magic Urban can influence the parenting roles of Nigerian women either positively or negatively. It also supports the idea that Nollywood films indirectly influence Nigerian society.

Research Methodology

The survey research design was adopted for this study. The sample size was determined using an online survey system sample size calculator with a 5,459,300 population, out of which a total of 385 women in Imo state were sampled from the three senatorial zones in Imo state with a confidence level of 95%, 50% accuracy rate, and confidence interval of 5. Due to the nature of the study, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique to distribute questionnaires to select women in Imo state. It was close-ended in structure with question items on a 5-point Likert scale. The data were presented in tables, and the frequency of occurrence was calculated using a simple percentage statistical method. Mean scores above 3.0 are considered significant by the study while Mean scores below 3.0 are considered insignificant.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Out of the 385 copies of questionnaires that were distributed, only 355 were returned by respondents with complete answers to the items on the questionnaire. These were used for the analysis. The tables are presented below;

Table 1: Level of exposure to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban

Indices	Rating <i>x</i>	SA 5	A 4	FA 3	D 2	SD 1	Total	<i>xi</i>
I have been exposed to programmes on African Magic Urban	<i>f</i>	207	110	13	22	3	355	4.4
	<i>fx</i>	1,035	440	39	44	3	1,561	Accepted
	%	58	31	4	6	1	100	88%
African Magic Urban made me aware of “Wives Round Table” programme.	<i>f</i>	113	162	23	47	10	355	3.9
	<i>fx</i>	565	648	69	94	10	1,386	Accepted
	%	32	46	6	13	3	100	78%
I am frequently exposed to African Magic Urban’ “Wives Round Table” programme.	<i>f</i>	180	102	30	36	7	355	4.16
	<i>fx</i>	900	408	90	72	7	1,477	Accepted
	%	51	29	8	10	2	100	83%

The first index showed that women in Imo state were to a great extent exposed to the different programmes aired on African Magic Urban with an 88% viewing rate. The second index revealed that at 78% rate, African Magic Urban made women in Imo state aware of the “Wives Round Table” TV programme. The third index showed that women in Imo state at a significant rate of 83% frequently exposed to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban.

Table 2: Level of Perception about “Wives Round Table” TV programme

Indices	Rating <i>x</i>	SA 5	A 4	FA 3	D 2	SD 1	Total	<i>xi</i>
Wives’ Round Table TV programme encourages quality parenting roles.	<i>f</i>	207	110	13	22	3	355	4.4
	<i>fx</i>	1,035	440	39	44	3	1,561	Accepted
	%	58	31	4	6	1	100	88%
The Wives Round Table TV programme teaches women different parenting skills	<i>f</i>	180	102	30	36	7	355	4.16
	<i>fx</i>	900	408	90	72	7	1,477	Accepted
	%	51	29	8	10	2	100	83%
Wives Round Table TV programme encourages me to be a good mother.	<i>f</i>	132	145	43	25	10	355	4.0
	<i>fx</i>	660	580	129	50	10	1,429	Accepted
	%	37	41	12	7	3	100	80%

The first index showed a significant 88% level of perception held by women in Imo state that “Wives Round Table” TV programme encourages quality parenting roles. The second index revealed that women in Imo state had a high level (83%) of perception of “Wives Round Table” TV programme as it teaches women different parenting skills. The third index indicates that “Wives Round Table” TV programme at 80% level rate encourages women in Imo state to be good mothers to their children.

Table 3: Level of “Wives Round Table” TV programme influence on women’s parenting roles.

Indices	Rating <i>x</i>	SA 5	A 4	FA 3	D 2	SD 1	Total	<i>xi</i>
---------	--------------------	---------	--------	---------	--------	---------	-------	-----------

There is now an improvement in my parenting skills.	<i>f</i>	159	103	53	37	3	355	4.0
	<i>fx</i>	795	412	159	74	3	1,443	Accepted
	%	45	29	15	10	1	100	81%
I can easily balance my parenting role with my career	<i>f</i>	75	183	55	30	12	355	3.8
	<i>fx</i>	375	732	165	60	12	1,344	Accepted
	%	21	52	16	8	3	100	76%
I am willing to advise friends and relatives on how best to relate with their kids	<i>f</i>	180	102	30	36	7	355	4.16
	<i>fx</i>	900	408	90	72	7	1,477	Accepted
	%	51	29	8	10	2	100	83%

The findings of the data in the first index revealed that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme influence parenting roles with an 81% improvement rate in parenting skills. The second index indicated that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme at a level of 76% rate has an influence on women in that they can easily balance their parenting roles with their career roles. Finally, the findings of the third index revealed that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme influence parenting roles at 83% rate as they are willing to advise friends and relatives on how best to relate with their kids.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are discussed in this section in line with the research questions and in relation to the reviewed literature.

RQ 1: To what extent are women in Imo state exposed to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban?

The results from the analysis in Table 1 reveal that women in Imo state are to a great extent exposed to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban. Based on the findings of the result above, the researcher answers the following research question: women in Imo state are highly exposed to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban. This is because they were exposed to programmes on African Magic Urban and because of their exposure to these programmes on African Magic Urban, it made them aware of “Wives Round Table” TV programme.

Findings have shown that women spend more time watching television than men. According to the assertion made by Lunden (2012), women no doubt spend quite a huge amount of time watching television, to the extent that it can almost be taken for granted that women rank higher than men. This is in line with the current study. Nielsen’s (2021) study corroborates this assertion by stating that when it comes to TV, women watch significantly more than men. Nielsen’s research indicates that women spend almost 40 minutes more than men every day watching straight television (4 hours, 11 minutes for women; 3 hours, 34 minutes for men. Hence, it leaves no doubt with the findings of the current study, which stated that women in Imo state frequently exposed themselves to programmes such as Wives Round Table on African Magic Urban, most especially when such programme centers on women rather than men.

RQ 2: What is the perception of women in Imo state about “Wives Round Table” TV programme?

According to the analysis carried out in Table 2, the kind of perception women in Imo state have regarding the “Wives Round Table” TV programme was revealed. The findings from the indices revealed that women in Imo state have a favorable perception about “Wives Round Table” TV programme aired on African Magic Urban. This is because the programme encouraged quality parenting roles, the programme teaches women different parenting skills and the programme encourages women to be good mothers to their children.

These findings are also relatable to the assertion of the Reinforcement Theory of Mass Communications, which states that the more that an audience of mass medium exposes themselves to certain ideas and stimuli, the more likely it is for them to accept such ideas and experience behavioral changes directly traceable to the communicated stimulus. The more women in Imo state frequently expose themselves to “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban, the more they learn new ideas on how to enhance their parenting skills. This in turn forms their level of perception about the programme. This is in agreement with the explanation of Evaristus (2021), that people’s conceptions of social reality, such as the Wives Round Table TV programme, are influenced according to their exposure level to such programmes on television. This shows that all this would not have been possible without their exposure to the programme. This is because their exposure to the programme has helped them in their parenting roles, enhanced their parenting skills, and encouraged them to become good mothers to their children.

RQ 3: To what extent has the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme influenced the parenting roles of women in Imo state?

According to the findings of the analysis presented regarding the level of influence of the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme on the parenting roles of women, Table 3 revealed that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme to a great extent influences the parenting roles of women in Imo state as findings from the indices have revealed that the African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme has an influence on parenting roles as 81% of the respondents stated that there is an improvement in their parenting skills. Based on the above findings, the researcher answers this research question by stating that: African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV programme to a great extent influences the parenting roles of women in Imo state. This is because there is now an improvement in the parenting skills of the women; the women can easily balance their parenting roles as a mother with their career roles, and lastly, the women were willing to advise friends and relatives on how best to relate with their children.

These findings corroborate the cultivation Analysis theory, which explains how people’s conceptions of social reality are influenced by their exposure to television content such as “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban. The theory simply assumes that people’s attitudes are forged in the hours they watch television, especially in the direction in which the content flows ideologically. This explains the willingness to advise friends and relatives on how best to relate with their children based on the influence exposure to the “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban has on the women in Imo state.

In addition, Asemah, Nwammuo and Uwaoma (2017), in their own contribution, which agrees with the findings of this study, stated that the mass media, particularly television, speaks to audiences and maintains society through images and ideas. This explains the ability of the women to balance parenting roles with their careers. In the previous findings, this factor was shown to be a factor militating the parenting roles of women. There now seems to be a balance courtesy of the influence of the “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban.

Summary/Conclusion

The findings of the study has revealed that “Wives Round Table” TV programme on African Magic Urban has greatly influenced the parenting role of women in Imo state and, as such, fulfilled the functions of broadcasting, which is to educate, entertain, and inform viewers with its various episodes. By means of educating, the findings of the study have shown that the programme has educated women on how to manage both their careers as well as their parenting roles as mothers, and the challenges faced in the family and how to overcome them. By means of information, the findings of the study have revealed that this programmes has kept parents informed with firsthand information from experiences from people and experts in the various fields being discoursed in each segment of

the programme. Therefore, based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that African Magic Urban “Wives Round Table” TV has an influence on the parenting roles of women in Imo State, which has brought about growth and balance in their career and parenting roles as mothers to their children.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

- i. Audiences should keep exposing themselves to media content that has to do with family and parenting as a lot of the time, meaningful family-related issues are discussed, and sometimes, solutions are provided for them through the media.
- ii. Broadcast media should constantly produce different family-related programmes, as that is first one of their social responsibilities to the people. They should also allot more time to family- and parenting related programmes, move on to create more awareness about them, and bring professionals onboard to give more details on parenting issues.
- iii. More professionals in parenting should collaborate with the media, especially radio and television, as they have the ability to appeal to the audio and visual abilities of the audience to come up with various parenting information as well as how to navigate factors militating against the parenting roles of women that will be vital to the people, especially mothers.

REFERENCES

- Asemah, E.; Nwammuo, A. & Uwaoma, A. (2017). *Theories and Models of Communication*. Jos: content analysis of traits using the stereotype content model.
- Egbai, M. (2019). The Impact of Television Advertising on Women in Nigeria and Iran Predestinasi. Volume 12, No. 1, Juni 2019, Hal. 37- 52. ISSN (Print): 1978-9351
- Evaristus, C. N. (2021). Impact of Social Media on Family Values. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies (SFJESGS), Vol.3, No.1 March, 2021; pg. 383–394 ISSN: 2734-2522 (Print); ISSN: 2734-2514 (Online)*
- Hernandez, E. (2012). *Using cultivation theory to analyze college student attitudes about the dating process following exposure to romantic films*. Unpublished M.A. Thesis Submitted to the Graduate Faculty of Texas Tech University.
- Johnson, A. (2021). *The cultivation theory of mass media*. Accessed at: <http://augusttustjohnnton> . Jos University Press.
- Lunden, I. (2012). Nielsen: Women watch more TV than men, but connected game consoles are changing that. <http://techcrunch.com/2012/10/05/nielsen-gaming-tv-console/>
- Neilson, S. (2020). The influence of viewing television and the effect of parental television mediation on violence behavior changes on children.
- Ngozi, E. (2017). *Balancing Career and Family: The Nigerian Woman's Experience*. New York: Doubleday.
- Pechu, A. (2014). Attitudes of TV audience toward commercial interruption in TV programmes. Retrieved from [http://: www.academia.edu](http://www.academia.edu)

Peterson, T. (2022). What Is Parenting? What Does It Mean to Be a Parent?, HealthyPlace. Retrieved on January 17, 2023, from <https://www.healthyplace.com/parenting/parenting-skills-strategies/what-is-parenting-what-does-it-mean-to-be-a-parent>. Last Updated: January 16, 2022

Sriram, A., Kumar, D. (2014). Impact of media on interpersonal communication among family members.

Thomas W. Valente. (2021). Mass-Media-Generated Interpersonal Communication as Sources of Information about Family Planning: *Journal of Health Communication: International Perspectives* Vol. 1, Issue 3, pg. 247-266.

Ukaegbu, M. I. (2018). *Understanding Models and Theories of Mass Communication*. Port Harcourt: Prelyn Fortunes Limited, 2019.

Vinney, C. (2019). *Cultivation theory*. Accessed at <http://www.thoughtco.com/cultivation-Theorydefinition-4588455>.